

REPORT

ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF A NATIONAL METHOD FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF ECOLOGICAL STATUS OF COASTAL WATERS IN GREECE, USING THE BIOLOGICAL QUALITY ELEMENT “ANGIOSPERMS”

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1. INTRODUCTION

At the Med-GIG (2013), five Member States (France, Italy, Spain, Cyprus, and Croatia) compared and harmonized their national methods for the assessment of the ecological status of coastal waters based on the Biological Quality Element (BQE) “Angiosperms”. In the IC process, seagrass experts agreed that the development of national methods should be based on *Posidonia oceanica*, due to its wide distribution, its ecological role and sensitivity, the existing knowledge and data on its responses to disturbance.

In Greece, the official method (accepted in the third IC phase, EC Decision 2018/229) for BQE “Angiosperms” in coastal waters is the *CymoSkew* index (Orfanidis et al. 2010) which is based on the seagrass species *Cymodocea nodosa*. However, despite that *C. nodosa* is common along the Greek coastline, its meadows are well-developed and suitable for applying the *CymoSkew* assessment method only in specific areas. To this end, *P. oceanica* being the only dominant Angiosperm in Greek coastal areas, is still considered as the most appropriate seagrass for the Ecological Quality Status (EQS) evaluation.

The experience gained through the application of the existing intercalibrated indices (mainly PREI) in the Greek monitoring network for the WFD implementation (2012-2019), has highlighted the need of a biotic index that can assess more efficiently the ecological status of *Posidonia* meadows in relation to anthropogenic pressures. The evaluation of the EQS based on PREI, obtained until today, seems to underestimate the EQS when compared with other BQEs (e.g., macroalgae).

This report discusses the first effort to develop and establish a national method, the **WePOSI (Weighted Posidonia oceanica Index)**, for the assessment of the ecological status of coastal waters in Greece, based on the BQE “Angiosperms”, using the seagrass *Posidonia oceanica*.

The development of the current assessment method, as described in this report, is based on data collected during the years 2013-2019 through the Greek monitoring network for the WFD implementation.

2. DESCRIPTION OF NATIONAL ASSESSMENT METHODS

WePOSI (Weighted *Posidonia oceanica* Index) is based on the principles on which already intercalibrated methods POMI (Romero et al. 2007), PREI (Gobert et al. 2009) and Valencian CS (Fernández-Torquemada et al. 2008) for the seagrass *P. oceanica*, are based. It is composed of 8 metrics, which are aggregated in a multimetric index, where different weights depending on metrics’ biotic level are given.

The selection of WePOSI metrics was based on a screening process where a dataset of 28 variables (metrics), ‘a priori’ sensitive to a variety of anthropogenic disturbances, were chosen and tested in *Posidonia* meadows of known and different ecological status (Gerakaris 2017, Annex A).

The selected metrics are commonly used in monitoring programmes, to interpret and quantify the main structural and functional features of *P. oceanica* meadows. These metrics belong to three different biotic levels: “population” (meadow descriptors), “individual” (plant descriptors), and “community” (associated flora/fauna descriptors) level (Table 1).

Table 1. The selected metrics used in WePOSI (Weighted Posidonia oceanica Index).

<i>Level</i>	<i>Metrics</i>
Population	Type of Lower Limit
	Lower Limit Depth (m)
	Meadow Cover (%)
	Dead matte Cover (%)
	Shoot Density (shoots/m ²)
Individual	Shoot Length (cm/shoot)
Community	Epiphytic Biomass (g/shoot)

All these metrics differently respond to changed ecosystem conditions, thus, to a series of anthropogenic impacts including nutrient increase, organic matter increase, mechanical impact (anchoring, trawling), industrial pollution, or fish-farming, among others (Martinez-Crego et al., 2008).

Overall, the WePOSI assessment method meets the criteria needed for WFD compliance. The selected metrics are combined in a final Ecological Quality Ratio (EQR), with five classes of ecological assessment (High, Good, Moderate, Poor, and Bad).

2.1. METHODS AND REQUIRED BQE PARAMETERS

Table 2.1. Overview of the metrics included in WePOSI (Weighted Posidonia oceanica Index)

MS	Full BQE method	Abundance	Disturbance sensitive taxa	Diversity
Greece	Yes	Type of Lower Limit Depth of Lower Limit Shoot Density Meadow Cover (*) Dead matte Cover (*) Shoot Length	1 selected sensitive species, <i>Posidonia oceanica</i> + percent of Plagiotropic Rhizomes, Epiphytic Biomass	No, only 1 species

(*) supporting metrics

Combination rule used in the method

In total, seven metrics are integrated into a multimetric index using the following equation:

$$EQR' = (EQR'_{MEADOW} * 0.5 + EQR'_{PLANT} * 0.3 + EQR'_{COMMUNITY} * 0.2) / 3$$

Where

$$EQR'_{MEADOW} = EQR'_{typeLL} + EQR'_{depthLL} + EQR'_{cover} + EQR'_{density} + EQR'_{plagiotropic}$$

$$EQR'_{PLANT} = EQR'_{shootlength}$$

$$EQR'_{COMMUNITY} = EQR'_{ephibiomass}$$

With

$$EQR'_{typeLL} \quad \text{value of LL type (progressive/erosive}=1; \text{sharp } 0.75; \text{sparse}=0.50; \text{regressive}=0.25)$$

$$EQR'_{depthLL} \quad \text{value measured - worst value/reference value- worst value}$$

$$EQR'_{cover} \quad \text{value measured /reference value,}$$

the ratio of the two supporting metrics, Meadow Cover and Dead meadow Cover, expressed as Meadow Cover / Meadow Cover + Dead meadow Cover (i.e., Conservation Index, Moreno et al. 2001).

EQR' _{density}	<i>value measured - worst value/reference value- worst value</i>
EQR' _{plagiotropic}	<i>value measured - worst value/reference value- worst value</i>
EQR' _{shootlength}	<i>value measured - worst value/reference value- worst value</i>
EQR' _{epiphbiomass}	<i>value measured - worst value/reference value- worst value</i>

2.2. SAMPLING AND DATA PROCESSING

Description of sampling and data processing:

- Sampling time and frequency: Once a year, July to August
- Sampling method: Sampling is carried out at predetermined sites of the national monitoring network at 15m depth. In each meadow, two sampling sites separated by 100m are randomly selected along the 15m isobath. At each site, three replicate 10 m transects are prepared following the 15m isobath and marked with pegs and buoys (markers for long-term monitoring). **Meadow Cover** (living *Posidonia* cover) and **Dead Meadow Cover** (*Posidonia* dead matte cover) are estimated as the proportion of living and dead patches on each transect. Close to each marker, over an area of 5 m², one 40x40cm quadrat is randomly selected to measure **Shoot Density** and **Percentage of Plagiotropic Rhizomes**. **Shoot length** is measured on 20 shoots randomly selected along the three transects. **Epiphytic biomass** is estimated on two adult (external) leaves collected from 20 shoots randomly selected along the three transects.
- Data processing: The leaves collected from 20 shoots (randomly selected along the three transects) were further processed in the laboratory. Epiphytes are removed and then dried at 60 °C for 48 hours (Dauby & Poulicek 1995).
- Identification level: Species level.

2.3. NATIONAL REFERENCE CONDITIONS

Detailed description of setting of national reference conditions

Because no truly unimpacted reference sites exist in the Mediterranean, and in accordance with what Mediterranean seagrass experts participated in the IC process agreed, a composite “optimal” site was constructed based on the WePOSI metrics with the assumption that this hypothetical site would have ecologically ideal conditions in relation to each of the metrics.

Contingent on the specific metric, this normative ideal would correspond to the maximum or the minimum value obtained (e.g., maximum for shoot density, minimum for epiphytic biomass). The optimum value of each metric for the composite reference site is derived as the average of the three best values recorded for each metric when all sites are included, and the 5 % of values excluded in order to avoid possible outliers. In accordance, the worst value of each metric is derived as the average of the three worst values for each metric.

In Greece, two different sets of reference values are proposed (Gerakaris & Panayotidis, in prep.):

- **Coastal areas under high natural environmental stress** (continental or insular areas with increased turbidity levels due to different causes: abiotic suspended matter linked with river inflows, abiotic suspended matter linked with intense hydrodynamic conditions, high trophic status linked with limited water renewal in enclosed bays) and
- **Coastal areas under low/moderate natural environmental stress** (continental and insular areas without river inflows, under high hydrodynamic conditions, and low turbidity levels).

2.4. NATIONAL BOUNDARY SETTING

Following the results of the IC process, the class boundaries are established by assuming that the system responds to all pressures in a linear way. While it is possible that this assumption may not always hold, thus far, no clear thresholds or discontinuities have been identified between the element quality and the pressure gradient. Thus, following the same boundary setting as POMI, PREI, and Valencian CS, the range from 0 to 0.099 was arbitrarily assigned to the bad ecological status corresponding to the absence (due to anthropogenic impacts) of the targeted seagrass (*P. oceanica*) and the other EQR boundaries were obtained dividing the remaining scale (from 0.1 to 1) into four categories of equal amplitude (0.225 each). Therefore, when *P. oceanica* exists, the EQR is computed as follows: $EQR = (EQR' + 0.11)/(1+0.10)$

2.5. RESULTS OF WFD COMPLIANCE CHECKING

Table 2.2. List of the WFD compliance criteria and the WFD compliance checking process and results

Compliance criteria	Compliance checking
Ecological status is classified by one of five classes (high, good, moderate, poor, and bad).	In Greece, <i>P. oceanica</i> meadows present four classes of ecological quality (High, Good, Moderate, and Poor). The fifth class (Bad) is only considered when an existing meadow is lost due to anthropogenic disturbances.
High, good and moderate ecological status are set in line with the WFD's normative definitions (Boundary setting procedure)	YES
All relevant parameters indicative of the biological quality element are covered (see Table 1 in the IC Guidance). A combination rule to combine parameter assessment into BQE assessment has to be defined. If parameters are missing, Member States need to demonstrate that the method is sufficiently indicative of the status of the QE as a whole	YES
Assessment is adapted to intercalibration common types that are defined in line with the typological requirements of the Annex II WFD and approved by WG ECOSTAT	YES
The water body is assessed against type-specific near-natural reference conditions	The water body is assessed against the best conditions of each individual parameter
Assessment results are expressed as EQRs	YES
Sampling procedure allows for representative information about water body quality/ecological status in space and time	YES
All data relevant for assessing the biological parameters specified in the WFD's normative definitions are covered by the sampling procedure	YES
Selected taxonomic level achieves adequate confidence and precision in classification	No taxonomy is needed for this method

General conclusion of the compliance checking: Compliance criteria are met.

3. RESULTS OF IC FEASIBILITY CHECKING

3.1. TYPOLOGY

In the Mediterranean, except for the BQE “Phytoplankton” (where a typology based on the degree of freshwater influence has been defined), the definition of a specific typology of coastal WBs is not considered relevant for benthic communities (e.g., marine angiosperms). Thus, only one Common IC type is used: Entire Mediterranean Sea, with no subdivision.

The Intercalibration of WePOSI is feasible in terms of typology in Mediterranean coastal waters.

3.2. PRESSURES ADDRESSED

Pressure

The WePOSI assessment method, as already mentioned, addresses a series of integrated anthropogenic pressures, including indirect and direct anthropogenic pressures in the Greek coastal areas.

Pressure indicators

The relationship between pressures and EQR values has been calculated using the LUSIsg index as proposed in Med-GIG (2013). A version of LUSI index (LUSIsg) that takes under consideration indirect (land-based: urban, commercial and industrial, agriculture) and direct (sea-based: mariculture, sewage outfall, harbour, sediment nutrient release) anthropogenic pressures along with the level of coastal waters confinement and background trophic status. All pressures have been quantified in a 3 km radius circle.

Amount of data

The study to test the relationship of WePOSI with LUSIsg was conducted in 70 sheltered to exposed *Posidonia oceanica* meadows (Figure 3.1).

Strength of relationship

A linear regression model was applied, and the resulting coefficient of determination (R^2), Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r), and p-value (p) were assessed (Table 3).

Table 3. Anthropogenic pressures addressed by WePOSI and overview of the relationship between WePOSI and the pressures.

Pressures	Pressure indicators	Amount of data	Strength of relationship
Eutrophication, organic matter and direct impact (direct habitat degradation)	A version of LUSI index (LUSIsg) that takes under consideration indirect (land-based: urban, commercial and industrial, agriculture) and direct (sea-based: mariculture, sewage outfall, harbour, sediment nutrient release) anthropogenic pressures along with the level of coastal waters confinement and background trophic status. All pressures have been quantified in a 3 km radius circle.	70 sites	Linear regression $R^2 = 0.702$ $p < 0.05$

Figure 3.1. Map of *Posidonia oceanica* studied meadows in the Eastern Ionian and Aegean Seas, Greece.

The pressure-response curve between LUSIsg and WePOSI is given in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2 Relationship between WePOSI and anthropogenic pressures, for which the combined pressure gradient is composed of the sum of significant pressures (LUSIsg Index).

Current results show that the relationship between the WePOSI and LUSIsg index is strong ($R^2=0.702$) and statistically significant ($p<0.05$).

The good and moderate ecological class are indicated by the green, and yellow colour, respectively.

General conclusion of the IC feasibility checking: The Intercalibration of WePOSI is feasible in terms of pressures addressed.

3.3. ASSESSMENT CONCEPT

The Intercalibration of WePOSI is feasible in terms of assessment concept. The assessment concept of WePOSI is similar to other IC countries because is based on the same sensitive species (*P. oceanica*) and follows the same strategy in which a set of metrics that includes structural and functional attributes of the ecosystem, is combined.

3.4. CONCLUSION ON THE INTERCALIBRATION FEASIBILITY

Given that the Intercalibration of WePOSI is feasible in terms of typology, pressures addressed and assessment concept, we conclude that it is possible to intercalibrate this method with the other methods based on the seagrass *P. oceanica*. The results of IC process (i.e., benchmark identification and standardization, common metrics identification, regression comparison, comparability criteria) for WePOSI assessment method with the rest of methods included in the IC exercise are given below.

4. BENCHMARKING

4.1 COMMON BENCHMARK

Identification of alternative benchmark sites in the Greek coastal areas.

The alternative benchmark sites are defined as locations of high status on the basis of low impacted areas (see below). The alternative benchmark sites are presenting very low pressures that respond to the following criteria:

- low population density: no settlement in the next 3 km (or less than 10 habitats/ha within that area)
- mooring density lower than 2 mooring ha⁻¹
- no harbour or mooring facility in 3 km
- no beach regeneration within 10 km
- no trawling in the area
- no industries within the 3 km
- no fish farms
- no desalination plants
- no evidence of meadow degradation due to other unconsidered impacts.

A set of alternative benchmark sites selected from all the Greek sea regions is provided in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1. Locations of alternative benchmark sites in the Eastern Ionian and Aegean Seas, Greece.

Validation of the selection of the alternative benchmark with biological data: In each alternative benchmark site it was established the EQR.

Description of boundary setting procedure set for the common IC type: The boundaries of WePOSI were set up according to an equidistant division of a continuum as no evident discontinuities were detected. As a consequence, the division of the ecological gradient in ecological quality classes with the class boundaries is very similar to the already intercalibrated methods.

4.4. BENCHMARK STANDARDIZATION

The benchmark standardization has been performed automatically with the excel data-sheet IC_Opt2_subSEAGRASS MED. The EQRs of the benchmark sites were very similar, so no further adjustment of the common metric EQRs was needed. For the normalization was used the subtraction option as the pressures behave in a parallel way.

5. COMPARISON OF METHODS AND BOUNDARIES

5.1. IC COMMON METRICS

The IC common metric used was a biological common metric: the type of lower limit of the meadows and leaf surface area per shoot.

5.2. RESULTS OF THE REGRESSION COMPARISON

Overview of the results of regression comparison are shown in Table 5.1, and Figure 5.1. The WePOSI assessment method presents a good correlation with the IC common metrics, therefore can be included in the IC exercise.

The Pearson correlation coefficient fulfills the requirement that $r \geq 0.5$. The slope of the regression fulfills the requirement that the slope should lie between 0.5 and 1.5.

Table 5.1 Results of the regression analysis (WePOSI EQRs vs ICM)

Member State/Method	R ²	r	p	slope
Greece / WePOSI	0.827	0.909	p<0.05	0.970

Figure 5.1 Greece: WePOSI EQR on X-axis versus ICM EQR on Y-axis

5.3. COMPARABILITY CRITERIA

Assessing level of boundary bias

The comparison of WePOSI with the other intercalibrated indices has been done with the excel datasheet IC_Opt2_subSEAGRASS MED (Figure 5.2 and Figure 5.3).

No adjustment is needed.

Figure 5.2 Comparison of WePOSI with the intercalibrated methods: GM boundary biases (GM- Good-Moderate class boundary).

Figure 5.3 Comparison of WePOSI with the intercalibrated methods: HG boundary biases (HG- High-Good class boundary).

6. DESCRIPTION OF THE BIOLOGICAL COMMUNITIES

DESCRIPTION OF THE BIOLOGICAL COMMUNITIES AT HIGH STATUS

At high environmental status, the hydrodynamic and light conditions are favourable for the growth of *Posidonia oceanica* meadows. Expected meadow coverage is over 90 % of the sea bottom, meadow distribution exceeds the depth of 35 m and often reaches depths down to 40 m. If present, dead matte is only limited and of natural origin (Boudouresque et al. 2009). Expected densities of *Posidonia* shoots are over 550 shoots/m² (at 15m depth), percentage of plagiotropic rhizomes is limited to less than 15 %, shoot lengths are over 95 cm (in July-August, the optimum growth period), while leaf biomass is over 1.5 g DW/shoot, and epiphytic biomass is limited to less than 0.1 g DW/shoot.

The leaves and rhizomes of *P. oceanica* are hosting an incredibly large number of associated fauna and flora species. Due to high shoot density, the biological community of associated organisms exhibits two facies: a photophilic community that grows on the leaves and a sciaphilic one that grows on the rhizomes (Peres & Picard, 1964). The photophilic community on the leaves is mostly dominated by macroalgae (mainly encrusting calcareous red algae), while the sciaphilic community on the rhizomes is mainly consists of red and green macroalgae. As far as the sessile animal component of the community, a large number of hydrozoans, bryozoans, ascidians are found fixed on both the leaves and the rhizomes. A rich vagile fauna is also present; many species (mainly arthropods, fish and molluscs), feed, reproduce and find shelter among *Posidonia* shoots.

In Greece, *P. oceanica* meadows hosting a biological community at high ecological status are present in the islands of Ionian and South Aegean Seas (e.g., Zakynthos and Kefalonia in the Ionian and the Cyclades and Dodecanese in the Aegean Sea).

DESCRIPTION OF THE BIOLOGICAL COMMUNITIES AT GOOD STATUS

At good environmental status, the hydrodynamic and light conditions are slightly different from the favourable for *Posidonia* meadows growth. Expected meadow coverage is 70 – 90 % of the sea bottom, while its distribution is usually limited at depths of 28 -35 m. Patches of dead matte are limited and mainly of natural origin. *Posidonia oceanica* meadows are dense, exhibiting shoot densities of about 400 - 550 shoots/m² (at 15m depth), the percentage of plagiotropic rhizomes is slightly higher (15 – 35 %), leaf shoots are usually 70 - 95 cm long (in July-August, the optimum growth period), while leaf biomass is slightly lower (1 - 1.5 g DW/shoot), and epiphytic biomass is slightly higher (0.1 - 0.4 g DW/shoot).

Since shoot density of *P. oceanica* meadows at good environmental status is still quite large, the leaves and rhizomes are still hosting a large number of associated fauna and flora species. However, the species richness of both photophilic and sciaphilic communities is lower. The photophilic community on the leaves is mostly dominated by encrusting calcareous macroalgae, but other filamentous red or brown algae also exist, while the sciaphilic community on the rhizomes is mainly consists of red macroalgae. As far as the sessile animal component of the community, a smaller number of hydrozoans, bryozoans, ascidians are found fixed on both the leaves and the rhizomes. A rich vagile fauna is also present.

In Greece, *P. oceanica* meadows hosting a biological community at good ecological status are present everywhere along the coastline, except the estuaries of the large rivers (e.g., Evros, Strimonas, Axios, Sperchios, Acheloos, Kalamas).

DESCRIPTION OF THE BIOLOGICAL COMMUNITIES AT MODERATE STATUS

At moderate environmental status, the hydrodynamic and light conditions are very different from the favourable for *Posidonia* meadows growth. Expected meadow coverage is 55 – 70 % of the sea bottom, while its distribution is limited at maximum depths of 22 - 28 m. Patches of dead matte are more evident and mainly due to human activities. *Posidonia* meadows are sparse, exhibiting shoot densities of about 250 - 400 shoots/m² (at 15m depth), the percentage of plagiotropic rhizomes is quite higher (35 – 60 %), shoot are usually 45 - 70 cm long (in July-August, the optimum growth period), while epiphytic biomass is higher (0.4 - 0.6 g DW/shoot) and proportional to leaf biomass (0.5 - 1 g DW/shoot).

The sparse *P. oceanica* meadows at moderate environmental status cannot support and host a large number of associated fauna and flora species, either on the leaves, or on the rhizomes. The species richness of the photophilic community is low, while the sciaphilic community is absent. The photophilic community on the leaves is mostly dominated by filamentous red or brown macroalgae. The sessile and vagile fauna component of the community is poor, and it is mostly dominated by a small number of ascidians, sponges, and sea urchins.

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ANNEX-A

The following 28 candidate metrics were tested for their potential use in the WePOSI index. The metric selection process included the evaluation of metrics' capacity to discriminate the different environmental quality levels (Analysis of Variances - ANOVA), the examination of a common pattern of variation existed among the metrics (Principal Component Analysis - PCA), and the evaluation of feasibility and cost- and time-effectiveness criteria.

Table C-1. List of *P. oceanica* metrics evaluated for their use in WePOSI.

Biotic level	Metric
Population	Type of lower limit
	Depth lower limit (m)
	Meadow Cover (%)
	Dead matte cover (%)
	Shoot Density (shoots/m ²)
	Plagiotropic rhizomes (%)
	Conservation Index
	Rhizome baring/burial (cm)
Leaf Area Index (LAI)(m ² /m ²)	
Individual	Shoot Leaf Surface (cm ² /shoot)
	Photosynthetic Leaf Area (cm ² /shoot)
	Shoot Length (mm/shoot)
	Number of leaves (n/shoot)
	Number of Juvenile leaves (n/shoot)
	Leaf necrosis (% leaves/shoot)
	Coefficient A (%)
Leaf Biomass (g/shoot)	
Community	Herbivore pressure (%)
	Epiphytic Biomass (g/shoot)
	Epiphytic Biomass/Leave Bio (E/L)
Physiological - Biochemical	N content in rhizomes (% dw)
	P content in rhizomes (% dw)
	Total n-s carbohydrates (% dw)
	d ¹⁵ N ratio in rhizomes (%)
	Epiphyte N content (% dw)
	Cu content in rhizomes (µg/g)
	Pb content in rhizomes (µg/g)
Zn content in rhizomes (µg/g)	